

An Empirical Study on E-Learning (Digital mode) during COVID Pandemic in Andaman and Nicobar Islands

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Introduction :

The Covid-19 pandemic has made digital learning an integral part of the educational landscape of Andaman & Nicobar Islands. However, the spread of digital education has been hampered by the great divide between the haves and the have-nots. Rural Andaman especially has been affected by the sudden reliance on online learning. Official statistics state that there are near about One (1) lakh students in the islands. But there is no clarity about how many of these students have access to online learning.

Education in Andaman and Nicobar Islands is imparted at different levels, including primary, secondary and tertiary levels. As per the official statistics available on the district portal of the union territory, there are as many as 396 schools in Andaman and Nicobar Islands which are spread over 36 Islands. Out of these, 306 schools are managed by the Department of Education.

Objectives of the Study :

- a) To study the quality of education in remote island.
- b) To study the initiatives of administration for E-learning.
- c) To study the challenges of students, teachers and parents during this Covid-19 pandemic.
- d) To study the problems of remotest island - Nicobar districts.

Data Collection :

- **Primary Data :** A survey has been conducted on all the three Districts of Andaman & Nicobar Islands which includes the villages of Cambellbay, Katchal, Kamorta, Hut Bay, Port Blair, Baratang, Kadamtala, Rangat, Mayabunder and Diglipur. We went from house to house for the survey regarding the online classes. We questioned them regarding the initiative by the administration for the online platform.
- **Secondary Data :** Some data were collected from THE DAILY TELEGRAM newspaper largest daily circulation of Andaman and Nicobar Islands, AIR Port Blair telecast (All Indian Radio). Few more data were collected from Administration website.

E-Learning/Digital Learning methods adopted by Teachers during COVID Pandemic :**1. Doordarshan Local Broadcast :**

This is a joint initiative by the Department of Education in collaboration with the Doordarshan, Port Blair to start the broadcast of pre-recorded tele-classes for the students of Class X and XII throughout the Islands from 20th April, 2020. A few highlights of this tele-class are as follows :

- One hour slot daily (5.15 pm to 6.15 pm) except on Saturdays and Sundays. Later the time was changed as 4 pm to 5.15 pm.
- Covered the subjects for Class X and XII (All Streams).

- English, Maths, Science and Social Science for Class X were taught.
- English, Physics, Accountancy, Geography, Chemistry, Economics, Mathematics, Business Studies, Computer Science, Political Science, History and Biology subjects were covered for Class XII.
- Classes taught using various teaching aids including Power-point presentation and other digital tools.
- Telecast covered the length and breadth of the Andaman and Nicobar Islands.

2. Online videos on YouTube Channel :

- The videos recorded for the tele-classes are also uploaded on the YouTube channel “AN Education Dept. Andaman”.
- The students who have missed any classes on Television or want to see the classes again will have an opportunity to view such videos online sitting at their home.
- More than 50 videos have been uploaded on various subjects.
- Good response from the students and there are hundreds of views on the channel.
- Tele-Quiz and Tele-poster competitions are conducted.
- WhatsApp groups are formed by teachers for students.

3. Repository of Digital content :

- Considering the demand by Parents for video and audio content, the Department has made a repository of the said content and provides the same to the needy students and parents through Common Service Centres (CSCs).
- Digital content is being stored in the State Data Centre servers and made available to the public through CSCs.
- Planning to develop a Digital Library of the e-content in coordination with the State Institute of Education.

4. Through Social Media Networks :

In most of the school, the teachers have formed whatsApp groups class-wise for the supply of study materials on daily basis, which leads to a huge relief for the students for note preparations. And even though the test are also been conducted through this media platform also.

Challenges :

- **Weak Internet :** A large part of the islands population has little or no access to the internet. This has been the biggest factor in hindering the proper penetration of digital education among the rural population. The lockdown imposed for many months also stopped children from gathering in one place with better internet connectivity. They were essentially cut off from education for months at a stretch.
- **Lack of Privilege :** Even if some rural areas of South and North & Middle Andaman are blessed with good internet connectivity, not many families can afford digital devices which are imperative for online learning. Families which rely on the mid-day meal scheme to feed their children properly cannot afford to spend thousands of rupees on a smartphone, leave alone a desktop or laptop. This lack of financial privilege has forced many parents to take their children out of schools.
- **Group Study :** In South and North Andaman, teachers have showed another innovative way to impart education during the lockdown. They have identified students who have a smartphone and internet access. They have then clubbed them with students who don't have access to internet. This makes for an effective group study which makes great use of limited resources.

The teachers send lesson plans to the parents who have phones. The other students note these down and finish their homework in their own homes. Then they send completed assignments to the teachers via the same phone.

- **Worst Effected Nicobar District :**

Andaman and Nicobar Islands is grouped with three Districts namely Nicobar, South Andaman, & North and Middle Andaman. During this Covid-19 pandemic the much effected students, parents and teachers are from Nicobar

districts because of low network connectivity. Perhaps there are many rural remote villages with no network connection. Internets are a dream for the people of Nicobar Districts. Nicobar, Nancowry, Kamorta, Katchal, Teresa, Galathia, Cambelbay, etc. are some remote villages of Nicobar districts.

Conclusion :

While these methods can work temporarily, they cannot offer a permanent solution. It is imperative to create a learning environment for children, while maintaining Covid-19 precautions. Covid-19 changed the scenario of learning, teaching, its quality, method and it leads to face more challenges to students, teachers as well as parents.

This crisis leads to finance crisis, education crisis, food and shelter crisis. In these islands the much affected were the remote villagers of Nicobar districts, they were not provided with proper cable network and mobile network. Hence, we are praising for the normalisation of the current situation for the betterment of students.

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